

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the problem of teaching English in Higher education. It studies the importance of project-based learning in teaching process and the ways of using this type of learning in teaching English.

The English language is developing in all spheres day by day, since the development of the world includes the most important two section: technology and the English language. The English language has already been like a bridge among the world countries in all fields: education, medicine, technology, politics, economy, social fields, science, industry, business, and other most important ones. On the other hand, most necessary sources; books, magazines, international journals, encyclopedias, are published; audio and video listening materials are recorded in English. Definitely, they should learn them, due to get better job and developing both their career and country as well.

For these several reasons, in Uzbekistan is being more paid attention to learn and teach the English language, even it is pointed by law. There are specific issues, on learning and teaching English language in Uzbekistan, of National system of preparing specialists; besides it retraining and preparing English language teachers makes

responsibility for the Ministry of High Education, that is why, it has several decrees on developing teaching methods and teachers' knowledge, making the best and modern condition at schools, lyceums, colleges, institutes, universities and other education institutions.

Teaching language is one of the most difficult and long-term process, in order to do it more effectively. As we know that there are four skills: speaking, listening, reading and writing. These skills are taught in separately and a different way with different approach. For these reasons, integrating all skills is one of the difficult and complicated tasks in teaching process. There are some approaches for integrated teaching and project-based learning can be alternative method. Project-Based Learning in teaching is totally practical and based on self-study, it improves learners' creativeness, autonomous and outlook. Using this method on teaching integrated skills widen students' all skills such as speaking, listening, reading, and writing which include grammar

and vocabulary as well. It is known that in developing of most nations' relationship period, it is very important to learn and use language in reality to communicate with other people in different nationalities. However, it is not enough, just being bilingual, owing to myriad people know more than two languages over the world. There is a very crucial question that improving people's thinking skills, at the same time, increase their mind and make necessary condition for working on themselves, not just doing everything as ordered, and directed. Project-Based Learning in teaching integrated skills has already been unquestionable solution in modern education system. It is proven that learning language is not easy procedure, though to speak in other language, even in target one, speakers must know what to say. Until this century, it is thought how to use language; nonetheless, it is pointed as just learning by heart as poem. In several research works, it is shown the upcoming, advantages and effectiveness, experience, different methods and background points of several scientists in education system of Project-Based Learning in teaching integrated skills. Project Based Learning has been pointing as the process of teaching and learning for ten years and most researches in this topic were done just in a few period, in consequence, it is modern method. In the next step of working on it, it should be found the effectiveness in reality, so in this review, the strength and weaknesses are looked through, checked and proved.

Project Based learning (PBL) is a figure or model that make the environment to learners with different interactive and sometimes simple, sometimes complex projects. According to the definitions found in PBL handbooks for teachers, —projects are complex tasks, based on challenging questions or problems, that involve students in design, problem-solving, decision-making, or

investigative activities which give students the opportunity to work relatively autonomously over extended periods of time; and culminate in realistic products or presentations.

It is necessary to purpose for the educational goals of learners, but not strict direction, it is incorporation of adult-learners skills. When learning process includes all, need skills it can be completely affective source for users. In order to widening the features of modern PBL, double important statement should be included that authentic questions and cognitive-technology-based as well. Besides them, increase in comprehensive school, social and community services and strict enough topics are equally important.

The PBL approach takes learner-centeredness to a higher level. It shares many aspects with TBL, but if anything, it is even more ambitious. Whereas TBL makes a task the central focus of a lesson, PBL often makes a task the focus of a whole term or academic year. Again, as with TBL, different teachers approach project work in different ways. Some use it as the basis for a whole year's work; others dedicate a certain amount of time alongside the syllabus. Some use projects only on short courses or 'intensives'. Others try to get their schools to base their whole curriculums on it. But there are generally considered to be four elements which are common to all project-based activities/classes/courses:

1. A central topic from which all the activities derive and which drives the project towards a final objective.
2. Access to means of investigation (the Internet has made this part of project work much easier) to collect, analyze and use information.
3. Plenty of opportunities for sharing ideas, collaborating and communicating. Interaction with other learners is fundamental to PBL.

4. A final product (often produced using new technologies available to us) in the form of posters, presentations, reports, videos, webpage, blogs and so on.

The role of the teacher and the learner in the PBL approach is very similar to the TBL approach. Learners are given freedom to go about solving problems or sharing information in the way they see fit. The teacher's role is monitor and facilitator, setting up frameworks for communication, providing access to information and helping with language where necessary, and giving students opportunities to produce a final product or presentation. As with TBL, the teacher monitors interaction but doesn't interrupt, dealing with language problems at another moment.

The advantages and disadvantages of PBL are similar to those of TBL, but the obvious attraction of project-based learning is the motivating element, especially for younger learners. Projects bring real life into the classroom; instead of learning about how plants grow (and all the language that goes

with it), you actually grow the plant and see for yourself. It brings facts to life. The American educational theorist John Dewey wrote "education is not a preparation for life; education is life itself". Project work allows 'life itself' to form part of the classroom and provides hundreds of opportunities for learning. Apart from the fun element, project work involves real life communicative situations, (analyzing, deciding, editing, rejecting, organizing, delegating ...) and often involves multi-disciplinary skills which can be brought from other subjects. All in all, it promotes a higher level of thinking than just learning vocabulary and structures.

In conclusion, students experience increased motivation, autonomy, self-study, scientific-working and affirmative attitude toward English and Project-Based Learning performs outcomes for both teachers and students, a good number of project-work supporters assert that the positive sides outweigh the negative ones.

References:

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